

QSAR with electrotopological state atom index. Part-3^a. Receptor binding affinity of estrogens and non-steroidal estrogen analogs^b

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Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) analysis of estrogens and non-steroidal analogs of estrogen with electrotopological state atom (ETSA) index has been performed in an attempt to explore the atoms or fragments of the molecules that are most important for the binding affinity to receptor. The study reveals the importance of phenyl ring fragment (C1, C5 and C10 atoms of steroidal estrogen, and C1, C3, C4, C9 and C10 atoms in case of non-steroidal analogs) for receptor binding affinity. The importance of these atoms or fragments is also supported from the literature survey. Thus, the phenyl ring constitutes the pharmacophore for receptor binding affinity of estrogen analogs. Hence, diagnostic potential of the ETSA scheme in identifying the atoms or fragments important for activity is revealed from the study.

Estrogens are female sex hormones that produce numerous physiological actions¹ including development of female reproductive system and secondary sexual characteristics, neuroendocrine actions involved in the control of ovulation, the cyclical preparation of the reproductive tract for fertilization and implantation, and major actions on mineral, carbohydrate, protein and lipid metabolism. The therapeutic use of estrogens is extremely widespread, and their pharmacological actions largely reflect extensions of their physiological activities. The most common uses of these agents are hormone replacement therapy in post-menopausal women and contraception, but the specific compounds and dosages used in these two settings are substantially different¹. The main use of antiestrogens is the treatment of hormone-responsive breast cancer^{2,3}. Treatment of female infertility is the most common use of these antagonists in gynecology⁴. The biochemical mechanism of estrogen action is thought to act primarily by regulating gene expression after binding with the estrogen receptor. Receptor binding sites for estrogen are located in the nucleus of target cells⁵ and exhibit both high affinity and low capacity. The lipophilic hormones diffuse passively through cellular membranes and bind to the receptors⁶. The present study deals with QSAR of biological activity in terms of receptor binding affinity (RBA) of steroidal

estrogen (SE) and non-steroidal estrogen (NSE) analogs with ETSA index to identify the important pharmacophores of the molecules.

Biological activity of drug depends on the types and magnitude of interactions between the receptor and the drug molecule. Various structural attributes of the drug molecule like electronic distribution, steric feature etc. are the determining factors regulating the interactions⁷. All QSAR studies for rational drug design are based on the notion that biological activity is the function of physicochemical parameters, structural descriptors, topological and/or electronic properties of the molecule⁷. Topological methods are probably the simplest ones because the parameters are easily calculable from the graphical representation of the molecules and do not require estimation of any physicochemical property. The arrangements of atoms across the skeleton, concepts of steric relations and molecular bulk, branchedness and relationships among various non-bonded parts of the molecule are considered in these methods⁸.

The ETSA index developed by Hall and Kier⁹ is an atom level descriptor encoding both the electronic character and topological environment of each skeletal atom in a molecule. It is derived from chemical graph theoretic ap-

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Table 1. Observed and calculated biological activity of estrogen derivatives

E 1 - E 20

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	Note	Biological activity [log RBA]			
						Obsd. ^a	Calcd. [*]	Res.	Factor ^{**}
E1	OH	H	H	H		2.000 ^a	1.866	0.134	0.292
E2	H	OH	H	H		0.845 ^a	1.406	-0.561	-1.224
E3	=O	H	H	H	R ₁ = R ₂	1.097 ^a	1.743	-0.646	-1.410
E4	OH	H	H	H	Δ ^{7,8}	2.253 ^a	1.545	0.707	1.545
E5	H	OH	H	H	Δ ^{7,8}	1.029 ^a	1.085	-0.055	-0.121
E6	=O	H	H	H	R ₁ = R ₂ , Δ ^{7,8}	1.041 ^a	1.422	-0.381	-0.831
E7	OH	H	H	H	Δ ^{6,7} , Δ ^{8,9}	1.574 ^a	0.894	0.679	1.483
E8	H	OH	H	H	Δ ^{6,7} , Δ ^{8,9}	0.556 ^a	0.434	0.122	0.266
E9	=O	H	H	H	R ₁ = R ₂ , Δ ^{6,7} , Δ ^{8,9}	0.250 ^a	0.771	-0.521	-1.138
E10	OH	C≡CH	H	H		1.875 ^b	1.660	0.215	0.469
E11	OH	C≡CH	OCH ₃	H		1.398 ^b	1.265	0.133	0.291
E12	OH	H	-CH ₂ (CH ₂) ₉ CON(CH ₃)CH(CH ₃) ₂	H		2.352 ^c	2.014	0.338	0.738
E13	OH	C≡CH	-CH ₂ (CH ₂) ₈ CH ₂ CON(CH ₃)CH(CH ₃) ₂	H		2.243 ^c	1.808	0.435	0.949
E14	OH	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₅ SO ₂ (CH ₂) ₃ CF ₂ CF ₃)	H		1.230 ^d	1.194	0.036	0.079
E15	OH	H	H	OH		1.230 ^e	1.523	-0.293	-0.640
E16	H	H	H	α-OH		1.900 ^e	1.406	0.494	1.079
E17	OH	H	H	H	OH19 at C1	-0.300 ^f	-0.268	-0.032	-0.070
E18	OH	H	H	H	OH19 at C2	1.850 ^e	1.715	0.135	0.294
E19	OH	H	H	H	OH19 at C4	0.840 ^e	1.470	-0.630	-1.375
E20	H	H	H	H		1.900 ^e	2.209	-0.309	-0.675

Obsd. = observed, Calcd. = calculated, Res. = residual. ^aAccording to eqn. (1). ^{**}Factor = Res./SEE. ^eRef. 16. ^bRef. 17. ^cRef. 18. ^dRef. 19. ^eRef. 20.

Table 2. Observed and calculated biological activity of non-steroidal estrogen analogs

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	Note	Biological activity [log RBA]			
						Obsd. ^a	Calcd. [*]	Res.	Factor ^{**}
N1	OH	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	OH		2.100	1.773	0.327	0.935
N2	OH	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	OH	Lacking Δ ^{7,8}	2.000	1.743	0.257	0.734
N3	OH	=CHCH ₃	=CHCH ₃	OH	Lacking Δ ^{7,8}	1.300	1.814	-0.514	-1.471
N4	OH	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃)	C1	OCH ₃		2.104	1.961	0.142	0.407
N5	OH	C ₆ H ₅	CN	H		1.585	1.907	-0.322	-0.919
N6	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ OH)	CN	H		0.929	0.750	0.179	0.511
N7	H	C ₆ H ₅	CN	OH		0.908	0.546	0.362	1.033
N8	OH	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ OH)	CN	H		1.740	1.990	-0.250	-0.715
N9	OH	C ₆ H ₅	CN	OH		1.292	1.786	-0.494	-1.412
N10	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ OH)	CN	OH		0.813	0.629	0.184	0.527
N11	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₂ NHCH ₃)	C ₂ H ₅	H		0.477	0.657	-0.179	-0.514
N12	OH	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂)	C ₂ H ₅	H		2.455	1.893	0.562	1.607
N13	OH	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₂ NHCH ₃)	C ₂ H ₅	H		2.155	1.692	0.462	1.322
N14	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₂ NH ₂)	C ₂ H ₅	H		0.301	0.677	-0.376	-1.076
N15	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ OH)	C ₂ H ₅	H		1.978	-	-	-
N16	OH	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ COOH)	C ₂ H ₅	H		1.301	1.804	-0.503	-1.437
N17	OH	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂)	C ₂ H ₅	H	R ₁ at C2 position	1.531	1.568	-0.037	-0.106
N18	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂)	C ₂ H ₅	OH		0.322	0.527	-0.205	-0.586
N19	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂)	C ₂ H ₅	OH	R ₄ at C11 position	0.362	0.405	-0.043	-0.123
N20	H	-p-(C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂)	C ₂ H ₅	OH		1.204	1.271	-0.067	-0.192
N21						1.518	1.362	0.156	0.447
N22						2.167	1.841	0.325	0.930
N23						1.875	1.841	0.034	0.098

Obsd. = observed, Calcd. = calculated, Res. = residual. ^aRef. 21. ^{*}According to eqn. (3). ^{**}Factor = Residual/SEE.

Table 3. Electropotential states (S_p) of the common atoms of estrogens

Compd.	Atom no.																		
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14	C15	C16	C17	C18	OH19
E1	2.147	1.845	0.409	1.959	1.363	1.090	1.231	0.730	0.646	1.484	1.202	1.154	0.164	0.684	1.202	0.994	-0.096	2.318	9.676
E2	2.147	1.845	0.409	1.959	1.363	1.090	1.231	0.730	0.646	1.484	1.202	1.154	0.164	0.684	1.202	0.994	-0.096	2.318	9.676
E3	2.125	1.827	0.395	1.942	1.341	1.060	1.190	0.669	0.604	1.454	1.140	1.054	-0.032	0.584	1.102	0.798	0.520	2.218	9.664
E4	2.106	1.817	0.380	1.915	1.286	0.927	2.381	1.574	0.505	1.415	1.133	1.113	0.095	0.544	1.133	0.953	-0.137	2.277	9.655
E5	2.106	1.817	0.380	1.915	1.286	0.927	2.381	1.574	0.505	1.415	1.133	1.113	0.095	0.544	1.133	0.953	-0.137	2.277	9.655
E6	2.084	1.799	0.366	1.897	1.264	0.897	2.339	1.513	0.464	1.385	1.071	1.012	-0.101	0.443	1.033	0.757	0.479	2.177	9.644
E7	2.037	1.776	0.335	1.838	1.124	2.114	2.218	1.433	1.437	1.274	1.028	1.061	0.054	0.475	1.092	0.925	-0.165	2.249	9.626
E8	2.037	1.776	0.335	1.838	1.124	2.114	2.218	1.433	1.437	1.274	1.028	1.061	0.054	0.475	1.092	0.925	-0.165	2.249	9.626
E9	2.015	1.758	0.321	1.820	1.101	2.084	2.177	1.372	1.396	1.245	0.966	0.961	-0.142	0.374	0.991	0.729	0.452	2.149	9.614
E10	2.116	1.820	0.383	1.934	1.323	1.033	1.155	0.614	0.562	1.433	1.097	1.000	-0.126	0.513	1.048	0.747	-0.918	2.216	9.720
E11	2.067	1.785	0.345	1.900	1.251	0.974	1.072	0.471	0.321	1.324	0.044	0.789	-0.278	0.418	0.989	0.688	-1.012	2.166	9.812
E12	2.218	1.896	0.411	2.011	1.376	1.072	1.213	0.676	0.592	1.511	0.633	1.159	0.091	0.636	1.184	0.976	-0.144	2.389	10.083
E13	2.187	1.871	0.384	1.985	1.336	1.014	1.138	0.560	0.508	1.460	0.517	1.006	-0.199	0.465	1.030	0.728	-0.980	2.287	10.127
E14	2.080	1.778	0.296	1.893	1.217	0.930	1.044	0.452	0.296	1.315	0.200	0.884	-0.140	0.456	1.042	0.834	-0.324	2.251	10.127
E15	2.088	1.798	0.368	1.913	1.299	1.003	1.113	0.554	0.523	1.400	1.083	0.984	-0.114	0.411	0.744	-0.563	-0.572	2.169	9.678
E16	2.147	1.845	0.409	1.959	1.363	1.090	1.231	0.730	0.646	1.484	1.253	1.247	0.371	0.684	1.007	-0.086	1.004	2.400	9.676
E17	0.507	1.845	1.972	2.182	1.363	1.090	1.231	0.650	0.507	1.238	1.125	1.106	0.130	0.634	1.170	0.971	-0.120	2.298	10.301
E18	1.999	0.414	1.824	2.108	1.445	1.138	1.260	0.700	0.596	1.403	1.173	1.135	0.150	0.664	1.189	0.985	-0.106	2.310	9.818
E19	2.221	1.993	1.824	0.494	1.199	1.005	1.183	0.700	0.596	1.403	1.118	1.135	0.150	0.664	1.189	0.985	-0.106	2.310	10.140
E20	2.206	1.891	0.451	2.006	1.427	1.177	1.349	0.907	0.769	1.568	1.371	1.416	0.649	0.957	1.464	1.452	1.462	2.549	9.674

Table 4. Electrotopological states (S_N) of the common atoms of non-steroidal estrogens

Compd.	Atom no.													
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14
N1	1.946	1.715	0.291	1.715	1.946	1.141	1.283	1.283	1.141	1.946	1.715	0.291	1.715	1.946
N2	2.005	1.750	0.314	1.750	2.005	1.264	0.411	0.411	1.264	2.005	1.750	0.314	1.750	2.005
N3	1.895	1.682	0.267	1.682	1.895	1.055	1.102	1.102	1.055	1.895	1.682	0.267	1.682	1.895
N4	1.820	1.628	0.210	1.629	1.820	0.898	0.852	0.620	0.915	1.946	1.932	1.938	1.932	1.946
N5	1.829	1.635	0.215	1.635	1.829	0.905	0.867	0.621	0.884	1.931	1.922	1.931	1.922	1.931
N6	1.987	1.953	1.950	1.953	1.987	0.978	0.867	0.621	0.884	1.931	1.922	1.931	1.922	1.931
N7	1.998	1.961	1.956	1.961	1.998	0.997	0.895	0.593	0.792	1.761	1.596	0.194	1.596	1.761
N8	1.773	1.591	0.176	1.591	1.773	0.826	0.760	0.541	0.823	1.886	1.886	1.901	1.886	1.886
N9	1.785	1.599	0.182	1.599	1.785	0.844	0.788	0.513	0.732	1.717	1.560	0.162	1.560	1.717
N10	1.942	1.917	1.920	1.917	1.942	0.917	0.788	0.513	0.732	1.717	1.560	0.162	1.560	1.717
N11	2.184	2.099	2.063	2.099	2.184	1.246	1.291	1.360	1.279	2.190	2.102	2.065	2.102	2.190
N12	1.975	1.740	0.281	1.740	1.975	1.095	1.186	1.283	1.220	2.149	2.069	2.038	2.069	2.149
N13	1.934	1.654	1.063	1.654	1.934	1.072	1.170	1.271	1.211	2.140	2.062	2.032	2.062	2.140
N14	2.171	2.088	2.054	2.088	2.171	1.233	1.275	1.347	1.269	2.179	2.093	2.057	2.093	2.079
N15	2.138	2.062	2.033	2.062	2.138	1.201	1.229	1.315	1.245	2.153	2.073	2.040	2.073	2.153
N16	1.862	1.594	1.011	1.594	1.862	0.985	1.062	1.184	1.139	2.080	2.011	1.988	2.011	2.080
N17	1.826	0.278	1.704	1.889	2.048	1.014	1.141	1.255	1.202	2.137	2.061	2.032	2.061	2.137
N18	2.144	2.066	2.036	2.066	2.144	1.187	1.214	1.255	1.128	1.980	1.743	0.289	1.743	1.980
N19	2.132	2.058	2.030	2.058	2.132	1.169	1.186	1.209	1.047	1.831	0.290	1.706	1.892	2.054
N20	2.156	2.032	0.821	2.013	0.905	1.201	0.145	0.151	1.293	2.214	2.114	2.071	2.114	2.214
N21	1.803	0.290	1.714	1.944	1.151	1.071	1.148	1.151	1.081	1.913	1.694	0.276	1.694	1.913
N22	1.795	1.606	0.180	1.606	1.795	0.867	0.846	0.592	0.797	1.772	1.589	0.174	1.663	0.860
N23	1.795	1.606	0.179	1.606	1.795	0.866	0.844	0.590	0.795	1.772	1.589	0.173	1.663	0.859

proach and has two basic components : (i) intrinsic topological and electronic state of an atom, and (ii) effect of the environment influencing the atom, considering differences in the intrinsic topological state of different atoms and topological distances among them which determine the magnitude of the interactions. The ETSA index has been shown to bear relationship with relative electronrichness or ionicity of different atoms, their topological status and relative positions among different substituents or groups. The ETSA scheme has been projected as an useful tool of QSAR studies and reported to have power to identify atoms or fragments in the molecules which are important for the biological activity¹⁰. The previous studies by Kier *et al.*¹¹⁻¹³ and also by our group^{14,15} focussed the ETSA indices as potential tool in the context of QSAR studies that may expedite understanding of the mechanistic aspects of drug action and determine the important fragments of drug molecules necessary for action.

Results and Discussion

The biological activity (log RBA) datasets¹⁶⁻²¹ of steroidal and non-steroidal estrogen analogs are shown in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. Calculated electrotopological states of common atoms of SE and NSE analogs are shown in Tables 3 and 4 respectively. The statistical parameters of the regression equation considered are r or R (correlation coefficient), EV% (explained variance), F (variance ratio) with df (degree of freedom), SEE (standard error of estimate). The 95% confidence intervals are shown in paren-

theses. The regression constants of all accepted equations are significant at 95% level (except superscripted with *) and F values are significant at 99% confidence level.

The single best electrotopological parameter was found to be the ETSA index of atom no. C10 ($r = 0.723$). Among the relation with two ETSA parameters, the best two relations involved C1 and C5 ($r = 0.812$), and C1 and C10 ($r = 0.786$) atoms. The ETSA values of C10 and C5 are autocorrelated ($r = 0.726$). Hence, an average of ETSA value of C5 and C10 was used along with ETSA index of C1 and indicator variable (I), which was used to accommodate α (zero)/ β (one) configuration or substitution at C17.

Thus the best relation is

$$\log \text{RBA} = -6.223 (\pm 3.738) + 1.014 (\pm 0.631) SE_I + 3.829 (\pm 2.570) SE_{\text{Eav}} + 0.4603 (\pm 0.450) I^* \\ n = 20, R = 0.806, EV = 58.42\%, \\ SEE = 0.458, F_{3,16} = 9.90 \quad (1)$$

SE_{Eav} = average of ETSA values of C10 and C5 atoms. SE_I = ETSA value of C1 atom.

Autocorrelation matrix (r) of eqn. (1), SE_{Eav} vs $SE_I/I = 0.227/0.022$ and SE_I vs $I = 0.109$.

The best three univariate equations of NSE analogs are due to C3 atom ($r = 0.707$), C4 ($r = 0.684$), and C1 ($r = 0.558$). From the bivariate regressions, the best relation in-

volved the C2 and C3 ($r = 0.750$), C4 and C9 ($r = 0.750$), C4 and C10 ($r = 0.745$), and C3 and C11 ($r = 0.743$) atoms. Among the trivariate relation of various combinations of atoms, the two best relations involve C1, C3 and C9 ($r = 0.790$), and C1, C3 and C10 ($r = 0.788$) atoms. C3 and C4 ($r = 0.88$), and C9 and C10 ($r = 0.90$) atoms are autocorrelated. Thus the best relation was obtained using an average of ETSA value of C3 and C4, and C9 and C10 atoms as predictor variables besides atom C1, and the relation is

$$\log \text{RBA} = 4.001 (\pm 3.695) - 1.984 (\pm 1.367) S_{N1}^* - 0.714 (\pm 0.648) S_{Nav1} + 1.539 (\pm 1.824) S_{Nav2}$$

$$n = 23, R = 0.794, \text{EV} = 57.18\%, \text{SEE} = 0.431, F_{3,19} = 10.79 \quad (2)$$

S_{N1} = ETSA value of atom C1, S_{Nav1} = average of C3 and C4 atom ETSA values and S_{Nav2} = average of C9 and C10 atom ETSA values.

Possible outlier, compound **N15** was removed and the following relation was obtained,

$$\log \text{RBA} = 4.715 (\pm 4.607) - 2.155 (\pm 2.098) S_{N1} - 0.796 (\pm 0.667) S_{Nav1} + 1.328 (\pm 1.307) S_{Nav2}$$

$$n = 22, R = 0.872, \text{EV} = 72.04\%, \text{SEE} = 0.350, F_{3,18} = 19.04 \quad (3)$$

Autocorrelation matrix (r) of eqn (3), S_{Nav1} vs $S_{Nav2}/S_{N1} = 0.284/0.679$ and S_{Nav2} vs $S_{N1} = 0.580$.

From the regression analysis it appears that C1, C5 and C10 atoms in steroidal analogs play the most important role to the binding affinity to receptors of the series of estrogen analogs. β -Substitution at C17 of SE analogs also increases RBA. This is further corroborated by the report that the phenyl ring is the structural feature responsible for high binding affinity to estrogen receptor²². Receptor binding sites for estrogen are located in the nucleus of target cells^{5,23}. Binding to the estrogen receptor is specific: epimerization of the 17 β -hydroxy group of SE (**E1**, **E4** and **E7**) to the α -configuration (**E2**, **E5** and **E8**) results in a less active estrogenic substance²⁴. The positive regression coefficients of S_{E1} and S_{Eav} in eqn. (1) suggest that such phenyl ring substituents which decrease the ETSA values of atom C1, C5 and C10 will decrease the binding affinity. This is supported by the report that derivatives of estradiol having additional methoxy²⁵ or bromo²⁶ group at position C2, and hydroxy substituent²⁰ at C1/C2/C4 of the phenyl ring have less binding affinity. Hydrogenation at C5 and/or C10 of SEs forming β - or α -androstane derivatives (which decreases ETSA value of C5 and C10) decreases the binding affinity to the estrogen receptor²⁰.

Again, for nonsteroidal analogs C1, C3, C4, C9 and C10 atoms were focused to be important contributors to the receptor affinity. It was also reported that NSEs act as

agonists/antagonists by competitive blocking of estrogen receptor^{22,27,28}: either or both the phenyl rings may be responsible for binding affinity. In the regression equations involving activity of NSE analogs with ETSA parameters, the variable indicating an average of ETSA of C3 and C4, and ETSA index of C1 atoms have negative coefficient. Changes in substitution that decrease ETSA value of C1, C3 and C4 will increase the RBA. Substitution by hydroxy group²², alkyl ether analog⁵ at C1, C3 and C4 of estrogen analogs, increases affinity. C2 atom also has similar type of influence on RBA as evident from bivariate relations.

C1, C5 and C10 atoms of SEs and C1, C3, C4 (ring A), and C9 and C10 (ring B) atoms of NSE analogs, i.e. the phenyl fragment, constitute the structural feature for binding to the receptors²². Importance of the benzene carbons (C1, C5 and C10 atoms of SE) in the relation implies that the substitution of the benzene ring influences the binding affinity. The variable indicating an average of ETSA value of C5 and C10 atoms (SE), and C9 and C10 atoms (NSE), and ETSA index of C1 atom along with indicator variable of SE analogs have positive contribution. Thus any change in substitutions that increases the ETSA value of these specific atoms along with β -substitution at C17 atom (SE analogs) will have favourable effect on the RBA.

Thus, electrotopological state atom index is a powerful descriptor of structural attributes and information content which may be correlated well with the biological activity. The potential of the index to focus attention on the fragment(s) of a series of congeneric bioactive molecules important for activity makes it an useful tool in the QSAR research and promote theoretical approaches in molecular design.

Experimental

ETSA index:

The formalism of ETSA index¹⁴ considers that each atom in a molecule is present in a information field composed of the other atoms of the molecule. Every other atom has an effect on a specific atom depending on the difference in electronegativity or electronrichness between them and also on their relative distance. Thus electrotopological state (S_i) of an atom i is composed of (i) intrinsic value (I_i , intrinsic electronic and topological status) and (ii) perturbation factor (ΔI_i , effect of environment),

$$S_i = I_i + \Delta I_i \quad (4)$$

The electrotopological state represents electronic distribution information modified by both local and global topology²⁹. The detailed formalism of ETSA was described in a previous communication¹⁴.

QSAR with ETSA index:

Tables 1 and 2 show the different estrogen (E) and nonsteroidal analogs (N), respectively, whose RBA datasets

were used in the study. The electrotopological states of common atoms were found out using a GW-BASIC program ELECTRO1 developed by one of the authors³⁰. The adjacency matrix in a specific format, along with intrinsic state values of different atoms, was used as input of the program. To the output file thus obtained, the biological activity data were introduced to make it ready for subsequent regression analysis. The program AUTOREG³⁰ was used to relate biological activity with ETSA index of different atoms and also to different combinations of them to find the best univariate, bivariate and/or trivariate relations. Using the program RRR98³⁰ regression constants with corresponding standard errors and various statistical parameters reflecting quality of the equations were found out. Autocorrelation among the predictor variables was also checked.

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